

Polarographic Reduction of Bromocresol Purple

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Polarographic reduction of bromocresol purple has been studied in McIlvaine, Kolthoff, Walpole and Britton Robinson buffers using KCl as supporting electrolyte. The $E_{1/2}$ is found to be independent of pH in the range pH < 4 and is shifted to more negative potentials as pH is increased. A tentative mechanism has been suggested for the electrode process.

SULPHONPHTHALEINS have been widely used as indicators for a wide range of pH¹ in industry and chemistry. These have also found application in medicine as the rate of excretion of phenol red has been used for determining the functioning of kidney. As an application to pharmacy methods have been developed for determining phenolphthalein polarographically in different samples viz., emulsions, tablets etc.

The present study which is the first attempt of polarography of bromocresol purple can be of great use in detection and estimation of this compound in different samples.

Method and Materials

All the solutions were prepared from A. R. reagents in conductivity water. The depolarizer, bromocresol purple, a Fluka product was purified from aqueous alcohol and its solution (M/200) was prepared in 5% alcohol mixture of water. The final polarographic solution was obtained by mixing 5.0 ml of this solution with appropriate amount of KCl (supporting electrolyte) and making it up to 50 ml with respective buffer solution so as to give depolarizer and supporting electrolyte concentration 0.5 mM and 0.2 M respectively. The pH of the final solution was measured by a Philips pH meter (model 9404). A manual polarograph (Toshniwal) in conjunction with a multiflex galvanometer was used for measuring potential (vs. S. C. E.) and current respectively. The dropping mercury electrode consisted of a standard capillary (E. H. Sargent and Co., U.S.A.) which had the following characteristics in 0.2 M KCl solution at 1.0 volt vs S.C.E. The polarograms were recorded at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and the deoxygenation was done by passing nitrogen. $h_{0.01} = 52.6$ cm, $t = 3.34$ sec., $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 1.809$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6}.

Results and Discussion

If all the buffers the wave heights vary linearly with square root of the height of the mercury

column at all pH values, thereby establishing that the waves are diffusion controlled.

The number of electrons involved in the reduction process has been determined by two methods namely, (i) determination of diffusion coefficient by Dawson cell² and subsequent application of Ilkovic equation and (ii) millicoulometry using method of DeVries and Kroon³. Results are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE-1

Buffer	pH	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² /sec	i_d μA	n (Dawson) cell Method	n (DeVries)
McIlvaine	2.2	7.8	Mean	3.25	1.828
			value		
Walpole	1.1	6.4	Mean	3.05	1.716
			value		
Kolthoff	4.0	7.3	Mean	3.12	1.771
			value		
Britton-	6.0	7.2	Mean	3.31	1.811
			value		
Robinson	9.0	7.8	Mean	3.05	1.748
			value		
Robinson	3.1	7.6	Mean	3.10	1.850
			value		
Robinson	11.0	6.0	Mean	2.65	1.790
			value		

Diffusion coefficients were calculated at different pH values in all the buffers and the results are in good agreement with the expected values⁴. The experimental values of 'n' (Table 1) can be approximated to 2. Such minor deviations are not uncommon⁵.

Slope values obtained from log plots record gradual increase with the increase in pH (Table 2). Thus reduction is facilitated by increase in hydrogen ion concentration and becomes increasingly difficult with decreasing hydrogen ion concentration.

From the $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots (Fig. 1) for the waves in McIlvaine, Kolthoff, Walpole and Britton-Robinson buffers, it is evident that there are two

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TABLE-2

Buffer	pH	$-E_{1/2}$ V S.C.E.	Slope mV
McIlvaine	2.2	0.395	22.0
	4.0	0.405	29.4
	5.1	0.460	31.0
	5.9	0.540	31.8
	7.0	0.645	35.0
	8.0	0.735	55.0
Walpole	1.1	0.255	42.0
	2.0	0.260	45.5
	3.1	0.265	48.5
	4.0	0.300	51.0
	5.0	0.385	54.5
Kolthoff	6.0	0.760	43.5
	7.0	0.850	45.0
	8.0	0.925	50.0
	9.0	0.960	51.5
	Britton-Robinson	2.1	0.320
3.1		0.320	32.0
4.0		0.340	35.0
5.2		0.440	40.0
6.0		0.490	38.0
7.0		0.560	37.0
8.0		0.680	44.0
9.0		0.720	50.0
10.0		0.840	50.0
11.0		0.960	70.0
12.0		1.060	75.0

d.m.e. appears to follow two courses—one at pH range < 4 and the other at pH range > 4. The number of protons (p) involved in the reduction courses in each buffer has been calculated^{6,7} from the ratio of the slopes of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots ($= \frac{2.303 p RT}{\alpha n F}$) to the wave-slope ($= \frac{2.303 RT}{\alpha n F}$).

While the slope of the first segment is zero, the ratio of the slope of the second segment to the wave-slope gives the value of p equal to 2. On the basis of $E_{1/2}$ vs. pH plots and the value of n (=2), the following two schemes for the polarographic reduction of bromocresol purple are suggested.

The fact that $E_{1/2}$ is independent of pH (pH < 4) suggests that either the required number of hydrogen ions are attached to the depolarizer before the transfer of electron or atleast the depolarizer is brought to a form which is so highly electron-seeking that though the electron transfer is accompanied by the proton but its concentration has little effect on it. Thus in the region where $E_{1/2}$ is independent of pH the following mechanism is suggested :

SCHEME I

The depolarizer is known to have a sulfone structure⁷ and the fact that it exists in this form below pH 4 is supported by the fact that in all the four buffers colour change occurs in the vicinity of pH 5. This is indicative of the fact that at this stage 'O' changes to quinoid structure (O₁) and follows Scheme II for the reduction :

SCHEME II

Fig. 1. Variation of $-E_{1/2}$ with pH in different buffers ; 1. Kolthoff buffer, 2. McIlvaine buffer, 3. Walpole buffer and 4. Britton-Robinson buffer.

segments in $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots. From this it follows that the reduction process of bromocresol purple at

Thus at $pH < 4$ 'B' predominates in the solution and reduction occurs according to Scheme I while at $pH > 4$ 'O₁' predominates in the solution and the reduction follows Scheme II. The fact that the stage where colour change occurs coincides with the break in $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots should be enough indication of two different mechanisms of reduction possibly involving two different forms, 'B' and 'O₁' of the depolarizer. 'B' with carbonium ion must be very reactive and though reaction 'B→R' involves H⁺ ions, quest of B for electrons is likely to be so great that the variation of H⁺ concentration in $pH < 4$ will have little effect on $E_{1/2}$.

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